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In the Age of Media Convergence; News Literacy and News Consumption Behavior of Undergraduates in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

This research seeks to find the news literacy ability and news consumption behaviours of undergraduates in Sri Lanka. In addition to that, the research explores the ability of young undergraduates to distinguish between reliable and authentic news sources from falsehood and misinformation. In order to collect the data, survey methodology was employed and primary data was collected through questionnaires. The research revealed that undergraduates consume news for various purposes and situations. Majority of them consume more news during pandemic especially in Covid-19 period and during election periods. Moreover, the research concluded that undergraduates also consume news to know national incidents and natural disasters. But few respondents do not have any specific reason to describe why they consume news. Significantly, it is revealed that social media is the main source of news consumption, Television is the Second and News website is the Third. Majority of undergraduates prefer Facebook, and YouTube. Majority of undergraduates have a habit to use media on a daily basis and consume around 45 minutes to 1 hour of news media a day. Furthermore, the study concluded that few but significant number of undergraduates do not use any kind of news media. This study revealed that most of the undergraduates have fake news experience and are not aware about the news media ecosystem in Sri Lanka. Hence significantly, they do not have the ability to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods to detect newsworthy content. Therefore, it is interpreted that undergraduates are able to get affected by fake news and more than half of the undergraduates are not news literate enough.

Keywords

Literacy, News literacy, Media convergence, Media Ecosystem, News consumption

Introduction

The concept of media convergence is being explained by several scholars considering various dynamics; especially how media operation has been entirely changing with fast growing technology. The Internet has dramatically changed the media environment, media industry, and professional practices of the field (Manovich, 2002). In the past 15 years, print newspapers have changed dramatically in content, design, and writing style in perhaps the most drastic manner either in completing or complementing with the emergence of online news outlets attracting advertising and revenue models that print media have jealously guarded for centuries (Tanikawa, 2017). This activity was previously limited to reading the newspaper or listening to a news bulletin on radio, or watching on Television. At present, audiences can get an 'instant happening' of the latest news, literally minutes old, on the Internet, or receive updates on their smartphones, in their email inbox or on their social network pages (Picard, 2009). It is obvious that technology has not only changed how the print media industry worked in the past, but has immensely changed how media content is being produced and circulated under one roof where a combination of print, Television, radio, Web, satellite etc. work together in one place.

Convergence and Media landscape in Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka had a population of 21.46 million in January, 2021. Among them 10.90 million are internet users and the number of internet users in Sri Lanka increased by 800 thousand between year 2020 and 2021 and the number of social media users are 7.90 million in Sri Lanka increased by 1.5 million of the total population in January 2020 (DataReportal-2021).

The Sri Lankan media landscape is broadening, and becoming extremely complex, diverse compared to what it was 25 years ago. With growing technology, media convergence has influenced the development of media in Sri Lanka, and how news content is produced for the consumers. Out of 8, top four media outlets identified by the Media Ownership Monitoring, at least five companies such as Capital Maharaja Organization, Asia Broadcasting Corporation, Power House, Wijeya Newspapers, EAP Broadcasting Company have more than one medium - TV, Radio, Newspaper under one roof. All of them are digitally connected and they make cross-posting on digital platforms. Almost all the media outlets use social media platforms to engage audiences and to promote their new programs.

It is apparent that every average citizen in Sri Lanka is exposed to a vast amount of information and news, from not only the mainstream media sources, but also from various internet sources, including social media. As Rasmin noted (2021), with an endless number of choices available, it has become extremely difficult to differentiate factual objective, unbiased and fair news from fabricated, manipulated, misleading, sensational, non-inclusive and persuasive media contents.

Media literacy and News Literacy

Positioning the discussion around News Literacy in the wider field of media literacy education is quite challenging but a significant necessity for the academics and for the society. According to Literature available, Media Literacy Education has its own history and development as one of the people's movements. However, media literacy education and research in a somewhat defined field of study started in the United State. At present Media Literacy has various fields of studies such as Media and Information Literacy, Critical media consumption, Digital media consumption, digital and media information literacy, critical media consumption. Media studies and information literacy education have their roots in early research about the ability to read, write and speak. More recently, scholars have considered the connection between these areas and the development of visual and computer literacy skills (Potter, 2001).

News Literacy is one of the most specific and narrowly defined areas of study, concentrates on how news is being produced, consumed and disseminated. In the information age, it is important for individuals to go beyond simply reading text since powerful visual images dominate the media and information landscape. Potter (2004) in his 'Theory of Media Literacy: A Cognitive Approach' comprehensively explains how we absorb the flood of information in our media saturated society and examines how we often construct faulty meanings from those messages. He observes that we psychologically protect ourselves by automatically processing the media to which we are exposed every day. Potter's (2004) cognitive model of media literacy offers a theoretical framework for the current study. Potter's model is useful because it considers several factors affecting overall literacy, including the knowledge that is necessary to be prepared for media exposure as well as the ways in which an individual processes information once exposed (Craft, Maksl, & Ashley, 2013). A Model of News Literacy brought together a range of conceptualizations in the research literature to create a cognitive model of media literacy with five components or five basic knowledge structures such as knowledge about media content, media industries, media effects, the real world and the self to interact with a person's combination of drives, needs and intellectual abilities.

News literacy is defined as the ability to judge the reliability and credibility of news content and source of information and ability differentiate between facts and opinions. News literacy is considered as a skill required for responsible local and global citizenship. The 'news literacy' invites readers go beyond surface level fact checking and to examine the media structures, institutions, practices, and routines that comprise news media systems (Ashley 2020). Critical contexts regarding news media structures and institutions should be central to news literacy education. Under the larger umbrella of media literacy, a critical approach to news literacy seeks to examine the mediated construction of the social world and the processes and influences that allow some news messages to spread while others get left out.

Research Problem

Youth pick their role models from media that hugely influence their socialization and development. Media messages hugely shape what they think, what they think about, and how they think. They believe everything appears in the news. These days, children and adolescents consume huge amounts of news and information far beyond the traditional media; TV, radio, newspapers, and magazines but through text messages via social networking applications where they do not have the opportunity to verify them for reliability. Sometimes, news and information that are biased, fabricated, manipulated, or not authentic have serious consequences on them. In many cases, mainstream media fails to uphold the principles of professional journalism and its commitment in providing verified, unbiased, objective, and reliable coverage on vital issues affecting the citizens. And the mainstream media as a whole, is predominantly owned by a small group of elites in power or politics who control the larger News and Information Ecosystem. This is a systemic problem that affects people's right to receive reliable and authentic news and disinformation and information falsehood have become a serious threat for citizens at large. Considering these, the research tries to find out the answers for the problem 'Are undergraduates in Sri Lanka news literate enough?'

Research Objectives

1. To discover the level of news literacy of undergraduates in distinguishing real news from different information neighborhoods.
2. To find out the level of competency of undergraduates to verify reliable and authentic news sources from falsehood.
3. To find out issues involved in the news consumption behaviors of undergraduates (knowledge on media ecosystem, knowledge about new media structure which includes content, ability to distinguish news from other information neighbourhoods, personal control and mindful consumption, knowledge and skills on verification and ability to detect newsworthy content).

Literature Review

The research studies on the news literacy in differently are well documented in existing literature, but, current scientific literature rarely examines the news literacy level of undergraduates in Sri Lanka in particular.

Though the path of media is being enlarged and diverged by the media convergence in the digital age, independence of news while producing news or in the content of news is questionable in Sri Lanka. Readership, listenership and viewership of news are dependent on several aspects in Sri Lanka such as some strategic policies, politics, business ownership and media professionals. A joint study conducted by [Verite](#)

[Research and Reporters Without Borders \(2019\)](#) has given the results, 75% of readership shared by just four business families, 70% of TV viewership is controlled by the top four owners, 74% of listenership is shared by top four owners, 80% readership shares of the print media accounted by politically affiliated outlets.

Some studies have observed that social media is an influential news source. One of these social networking sites, Facebook, has become a popular social networking site for today's Sri Lankan youth. Among social media, Facebook, being the second most visited website in the world and the most visited in Sri Lanka, can be identified as a special source of addiction. Today, the average user views Facebook for at least 30 minutes a day as a practice that uses smart computers or devices and is displayed in a variety of Facebook content ([Andreassen et al, 2013](#)). According to the survey of Centre for Policy Alternatives (CPA), Facebook is the most popular source of news for those aged 18 to 24 and ten percentage of people do not trust the any news media and all media outlets are the same to them. According to [Newman \(2009\)](#), social media and user generated content is increasingly moving centre stage; influencing the strategic direction and practice of journalism. One of the core outcomes of the media convergence is plenty of news: accessibility of news all the time through multiple devices; competition amongst new media organizations to produce fast-tacked news; breaking news; and news 24/7.

As per the Sri Lankan Media Audience Study-2019 which was published in Sri Lanka by [International Media Support \(2020\)](#), found that, 77% of Sri Lankans indicated that news was very important to them. 54% rely on word of mouth to get news, 39% use newspapers regularly to get news, 31% of the total sample receive news from social media and across various demographics, Sri Lankan audiences highly value news and current information. More than three quarters (77%) identified news as being very important, and another 18% said it was somewhat important. Most of the people turn to two, three or four news sources on a regular basis apparently to guard against being misled by media biases and manipulation.

[The National Survey of Bangladesh regarding new Literacy \(2020\)](#), revealed that a large proportion of individuals do not utilize any form of news media and Fake news has reached two-thirds of the population. Fake news has been experienced by 76 percent of men and 51 percent of women. Only a few individuals double-check the news. The most common method of cross-checking news is to compare the same news from many sources before making a judgment. The majority of participants stated that they do not believe what they see on social media right immediately ([Chowdhury, 2020](#)).

Materials and methods

In order to carry out the objectives of the research, both qualitative and quantitative data methods such as primary and secondary data which represent the audience's viewpoints. The survey method was used to collect data and required data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire which was distributed

among the respondents. The questionnaire consisted close ended questions in English, Sinhala and Tamil languages. Once drafted, the questionnaire pre-tested and validated before it was used for the actual study.

The Simple Random Sampling technique was employed to draw the sample from the population and the sample size was 200 undergraduates. Participants were invited to participate in a web-based online survey (shared via Gmail) which took approximately 30 minutes to complete. Samples were selected widely from all faculties randomly via WhatsApp groups, Facebook groups and all available social media networks. This survey was conducted including all 5 departments and undergraduates from all years of Trincomalee campus of Eastern University. Among them 41.85% of respondents are from Languages and Communication studies, 34.2% respondents are from Business and Management studies, other 23.95% of respondents are from Department of Computer Science, Department of Applied Science and Unit of Siddha Medicine. Out of the 200 respondents 49.6% of students do not have the academic knowledge in the field of journalism.

Data analysis and Findings

4.1 Sources of News Consumption

From the findings of study, it became evident that social media is the main source of news consumption and 55.8% of undergraduates consume news from social media. Television comes Second as 43.2% and News website is the third news source (7.7%).

Figure 1 : Sources of news consumption

According to the findings, it is obvious that majority number of undergraduates use Facebook (43.35%) and YouTube (36.05%) to be informed daily. They use WhatsApp (26.15%), Viber (24.1%), and Instagram (20.5%) too. It is evident that a significant number of undergraduates (9.25%) do not use any kind of news media.

The study has found that, all respondents have a habit to use media on a daily basis. Almost 15% of respondents used to consume media for news 45 minutes - 1 hour in a day. The highest number of undergraduates spends less than 30 minutes consuming news per day via media; They spend 50.2% with social media, 27% with television, 37.35% with newspapers (printed), 34.05% with radio, 28.2% with websites and 37.45% by word of mouth. Furthermore, it is analyzed that a lesser amount of undergraduates consumes news more than 5 hours per day. Therefore, heavy users are lesser. Undergraduates spend more time on social media in order to consume news. 21.35% of respondents spend more than 5 hours daily in consuming news on social media. Moreover, 18.25% of respondents agree that they consume news from their favorite news channels only. 43.95% of them neutrally accepted this statement.

4.2 Purposes and situations of news consumption

From the findings of study, it became evident that undergraduates consume news for various purposes. Undergraduates especially consume more news during pandemic especially in Covid-19 period (50%), and during election periods (43.4%). 31.1% of respondents consume news to know natural disasters and national incidents (19.4%). 16.1% of undergraduates more likely to consume news when any changes happen in government regulations. They consume news to know sports events (11.3%), and gossips spreading regarding a celebrity (6.4%). Significantly, 12.1% of respondents do not have any special moments to describe why they consume news.

Figure 2: Purposes and situations of news consumption

4.3 News consumption behavior

According to figure 3 which indicates consumption behavior and pattern of undergraduates, significantly 42.1% of undergraduates prefer to do something that challenges the thinking abilities and while 10.4% of respondents prefer for complex problems. Therefore, it is interpreted that most of the undergraduates prefer to use critical thinking to verify the newsworthiness of the news content. 33% of undergraduates do not like to think too much when they consume news, 14.6% of undergraduates try to avoid situations that require thinking in depth of news.

Figure 3: News consumption behavior

Moreover, the findings of the study revealed that almost 72.97% of undergraduates have fake news experience which can be divided as very frequently, frequently and rarely. 11.41% of undergraduates experienced this situation very frequently, 26.61% of undergraduates are frequently and 34.45% of undergraduates are rarely experienced.

4.4 Knowledge on Media Ecosystem

Respondents were asked several questions to get to know how they are knowledgeable about the news media ecosystem. Out of 191 respondents 47% of respondents directly stated that they do not know regarding the questions itself and 33% of respondents gave wrong answers about the knowledge and Media ecosystem of Sri Lanka. Therefore, it is interpreted that 80% of respondents are not aware about the news media ecosystem in Sri Lanka. Only 25.3% of respondents were knowledgeable on media outlets in Sri Lanka work as non-profit businesses and most of them are owned by the government. 74.85% of respondents do not have any idea about complaining about the issues related to the accuracy of content presented in print media. Out of them, 43.15% do not even know whether there is a self-regulatory body to complain against the content of print media in Sri Lanka. There are other questions which are related to media ecosystem asked in questionnaire are, media outlets which are owned by same companies (conglomerate), cable based

media in Sri Lanka, media companies which have publicly own gossip sites, websites in Sri Lanka which are positioned in the top 10 of Alexa ranking, editor’s responsibility in published items, possible effects on the dependence on advertising of news for the purpose of money making, fact-checking organizations in Sri Lanka. According to the answers given, it is interpreted that more than three-quarter of undergraduates are less literate in the media ecosystem of Sri Lanka.

Figure 4 : **Knowledge on Media Ecosystem**

4.5 Ability to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods

In the questionnaire, there were some statements mentioned to check the ability of respondents to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods, especially whether they are able to identify the opinion statements which cover the title of the stories. So, actual headlines were given to identify their ability. Moreover, they were asked to distinguish news from columns in newspapers, news from entertainment, find advertorial statements, identify paid content, purpose of mentioning the names of political parties in party sponsored ads etc.

After responding, it is identified that 35.75% of undergraduates have the ability to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods, 64.23% of undergraduates do not have the ability to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods. Among 62.43%, 33.13% of undergraduates directly have mentioned that they do not know how to distinguish news and 31.1% of students tried to answer but got wrong by answers.

Figure 5: **Ability to distinguish news from other neighborhoods**

4.6 Knowledge and Skills on Verification

In the questionnaire, there was a question which included a picture of the original person as well as a manipulated picture of that person along with. 56.5% of undergraduates identified that the picture was manipulated. 18.1% of undergraduates answered in a doubtful manner. They agreed that sometimes this picture can be manipulated and they are not in a position to confidently mention that. 13.5% of students directly mentioned that they do not know the answer (see figure 6).

Figure 6: **Knowledge and Skills on Verification**

There was a question to identify the skills on partiality in news. 28.3% of respondents mentioned as they can not detect easily about bias in news, 17.75% of respondents stated as mainstream media is less biased outlets, 33.65% of respondents think bias is something unavoidable, 1.65% of respondents stated bias as a beneficial aspect, 18.65% of respondents do not have any idea about bias in media.

4.7 Ability in identifying newsworthy content

According to Figure 7, it is revealed that 28.01% have ability to identify newsworthy content, 78.99% of respondents do not have sufficient knowledge in detecting newsworthy content.

Figure 7: Ability in identifying newsworthy content

Conclusion

People have a right know the information and truth to be educated and to be self-governing individuals. In the age of disinformation and information falsehood, it is important to know who creates and distributes media information or messages, who is responsible for it and need to have the ability to detect newsworthy content.

Undergraduates in Sri Lanka consume news to get to be informed about the public events and incidents around them and to take actions. Majority of them had been consumed more news during pandemic especially in Covid-19 period and during election periods. Less but still significant number of undergraduates do not have any idea why they consume news. And it is concluded that undergraduates' main source of news consumption is social media and they use Facebook heavily. They use YouTube, WhatsApp, viber and Instagram also.

It is interpreted positively that most of the undergraduates those who have academic knowledge on media and journalism preferred to use critical thinking to verify the newsworthiness of the news content and experienced fake news experience too. Some of the undergraduates have the ability to distinguish news from other information neighborhoods. But most of the undergraduates do not have sufficient knowledge in detecting newsworthy content. So that, they need be armed with knowledge with fact checking and visually discovering similar images to consume news in a secured way.

Less but significant number of undergraduates have the news media knowledge that includes media structures, media content, knowledge and skills on verification and ability to detect newsworthy content. But most of the undergraduates are not aware about the News Media Ecosystem in Sri Lanka. Most of them do not have any idea about complaining about the issues related to the accuracy of content presented in print media and do not even know there is a self-regulatory body to complain against the content of print media in Sri Lanka. Therefore, it is interpreted that more than three-quarter of undergraduates are less literate in the media ecosystem of Sri Lanka.

It is interpreted that all information is not created equal and news consumers are able to get affected by fake news. News literacy would assist individuals in determining what they should trust, share, and act on based on the inspiring criteria of excellent journalism. News literacy is essential for equipping individuals with the skills and knowledge they need to comprehend how the news media operates in today's world.

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